

D6.3

Datasets of collected data

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Deliverable 6.3 Datasets of collected data

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1.2	12.03.2025	Ruth M. Córdoba	Add Descriptions after internal revision

Datasets associated with the deliverable

Multispectral orthomosaic (J00006) - <https://zenodo.org/records/15315144>

Multispectral orthomosaic (J00007) - <https://zenodo.org/records/15319428>

Multispectral orthomosaic (J00009) - <https://zenodo.org/records/15322300>

Multispectral orthomosaic (MA00001) – <https://zenodo.org/records/15349942>

All other products obtained during this work, described in section 3 “Results”, are available on request (info@soilolive.eu).

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

ELD	Economics of Land Degradation Initiative
JRC	European Commission’s Joint Research Centre
EEA	European Environment Agency
EU	European Union

Executive Summary

This document presents a comprehensive overview of the data collection, methods, and information gathered for the project through drone-based remote sensing. Numerous drone flights have been conducted over various olive groves using different sensors, including multispectral, RGB, and thermal cameras. The objective is to obtain georeferenced data to analyze both soil composition and the vegetation present in the surveyed fields.

1. Introduction

SOIL O-LIVE - *The soil biodiversity and functionality of mediterranean olive groves*, is a project funded by the EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe, Under Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, aimed at assessing the environmental condition of olive grove soils on a large scale in the major Mediterranean olive production areas. SOIL O-LIVE has several aims: 1) examine

between soil health and the quality and safety of olive oil, 3) implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices, and 4) establish strict ecological thresholds for healthy European olive groves.

This report outlines the data acquisition and processing methods employed in the SOIL-OLIVE project. The objective was to capture and analyze data from various groves using drone flights equipped with RGB, multispectral, and thermal cameras. The captured data were processed to generate several products, including orthomosaics, vegetation indices, point clouds, and Digital Elevation Models (DEM).

2. Methods and Materials

Different drones and sensors have been employed, selected based on the desired outputs and the extent of the surveyed area. Given the battery limitations of these devices, flights over larger areas prioritize drones with longer battery life. All surveyed fields have been subject to data collection flights, and corresponding products have been generated accordingly.

2.1 Dataset acquisition

Data has been gathered using RGB, thermal, hyperspectral, and multispectral sensors. These sensors provide valuable products such as RGB, multispectral, and thermal orthomosaics, as well as point clouds. All datasets are georeferenced, ensuring spatial accuracy and facilitating further analysis.

Drone flights were conducted across multiple olive groves, each with specific dates and types of sensors used. The primary sensors included:

- **RGB Cameras:** Used to capture high-resolution images of the fields and generate precise point cloud datasets.
- **Multispectral Cameras (Micasense and DJI3M):** Used to capture data across different wavelengths to generate vegetation indices.
- **Thermal Cameras (H20T and DJI3T):** Used to capture temperature variations within the fields.

2.2 Data processing and products generated

The generated products are obtained using specialized software that enables photogrammetric reconstruction and the creation of digital elevation, surface, and terrain models. These processes result in orthomosaics, where each pixel is spatially corrected and contains specific information based on the sensor used for data acquisition, whether multispectral or thermal.

The captured data were processed to produce the following products:

- **RGB Orthomosaics:** High-resolution, composite images of the fields.
- **Multispectral Orthomosaics and Vegetation Indices:** Composite images and indices such as NDVI derived from multispectral data.
- **Thermal Orthomosaics:** Composite thermal images showing temperature variations.
- **Point Clouds (NdP):** 3D models generated from RGB and multispectral data.
- **Digital Elevation Models (DEM):** 3D representations of the terrain.

3. Results

As previously mentioned, various products have been generated through this process. This section provides a series of links granting access to the generated outputs, ensuring free availability to all interested parties.

The following tables summarize the data captured and products generated for each olive farm:

J00006 - Jaén (Los Racioneros)

Date	Data Captured	Products Generated
14-02-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense)	
08-03-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB (DJI)	
27-04-2023	Thermal (H20T), RGB	
02-05-2023	Thermal (H20T), RGB	
09-05-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB	
12-05-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB	
14-06-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB	
20-06-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB	
22-06-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB	

Date	Data Captured	Products Generated
24-06-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (Micasense), RGB	
09-09-2023	Thermal (DJI3T, H20T), Multispectral (DJI3M, Micasense), RGB (DJI)	Orthomosaic_Indices
20-09-2023	Thermal (DJI3T, H20T), Multispectral (DJI3M, Micasense), RGB (DJI)	Orthomosaic_Indices
27-09-2023	Thermal (DJI3T, H20T), Multispectral (DJI3M, Micasense), RGB (DJI)	
06-10-2023	Thermal (DJI3T, H20T), Multispectral (DJI3M, Micasense), RGB (DJI)	
10-10-2023	Thermal (H20T), Multispectral (DJI3M), RGB	
01-11-2023	Thermal (H20T), RGB	
07-11-2023	RGB (P1)	DEM, Point Cloud (NdP), RGB Orthomosaic
05-04-2024	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M), RGB (P1)	RGB Orthomosaic, DEM_RGB, NdP

J00007 - Jaén (Santisteban del Puerto)

Date	Data Captured	Products Generated
28-11-2023	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M), RGB (P1)	DEM, Point Cloud (NdP), RGB Orthomosaic, Orthomosaic_Indices
17-03-2024	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M)	Multispectral_NdP Orthomosaic_Indices

MA00001 - Málaga (Antequera)

Date	Data Captured	Products Generated
22-09-2023	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M), RGB (P1)	Thermal Orthomosaic, DEM, Point Cloud (NdP), RGB Orthomosaic, Orthomosaic_Indices
14-02-2023	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M), RGB (P1)	DEM, Point Cloud (NdP), RGB Orthomosaic, Orthomosaic_Indices

J00009 - Sabiote

Date	Data Captured	Products Generated
16-03-2024	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M)	
18-04-2024	Thermal (DJI3T), Multispectral (DJI3M)	

4. Conclusions

The SOIL-OLIVE project has successfully captured extensive data across multiple olive farms using advanced drone technology. The processed data have resulted in valuable products, including various types of orthomosaics, vegetation indices, and 3D models, which are essential for the analysis and management of the olive fields.